

DECODING QUANTUM, DECODING THE UNIVERSE

Part 3. TRANZERAR is origin of the Universe, locate it by a device.

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Abstract.

Analyzing observed data in the area of 93 billion light years, combine with the quantum structure of the universe, we have discovered that the Universe is formed and operated according to Quantum laws, and invent a device to detect the Tranzerar.

Decoding Quantum, decoding the Universe.

QUANTUM are perfect physical entities, have the power to operate the Universe, are the source of all movement. Quantum create all matter, planets, life,... and the majestic Universe.

Nice Earth, be ready to receive the “QUANTUM CODE”, is the key to decode all the mysteries of science, upgrade science and technology to the Quantum level.

Quantum is the origin of everything and all physical phenomena, combine with deep physics thinking, will solve all the problems of science, and invent many technologies to make life better.

Holding the Quantum code, nothing is mysterious anymore.

This scientific work has 8 parts, see details of each part in the separate publication. After scientific community review and confirmation, the entire Quantum code will be published fully. Now, details of part 3 will be published first.

1. INTRODUCTION.

Part 1. Quantum decoding, is the key to decode all the mysteries of science.

The scientist Issac Newton discovered a part of Quantum about 340 years ago.

QUANTUM is the origin of everything and all physical phenomena, combine with deep physics thinking, will solve all the problems of science, and invent many technologies to make life better.

Part 2. Earth and Solar System are formed and operated by Quantum.

Based on archaeological data, combining Quantum codes, physical analysis of celestial bodies, connect all evidence on the entire Earth, we have calculated and discovered the origin of Earth and the Solar System.

Part 3. TRANZERAR is origin of the Universe, locate it by a device.

Analyzing observed data in the area of 93 billion light years, combine with Quantum structure, we have discovered that the Universe is formed and operated according to Quantum laws, and invent a device to detect the Tranzerar.

Part 4. Quantum cycle of the Universe, answers the age, beginning, end point and limit of the Universe.

Quantum will let us know the Universe operates according to the Quantum cycle, and will know the limit of the Universe. Analyzing the operation of celestial bodies, will calculate the age of each part of the Universe.

Part 5. The Earth is operated by Quantum, analysis to determine the natural disasters impending.

After studying parts 1-2-3-4, now we have understood everything:

Understanding the Earth operated by Quantum, will know the origin of natural disasters such as volcanoes, earthquakes, tsunamis..., so will determine the time and extent it occurs, will prevent, reduce damage a lot.

Part 6. The interesting origin of the Moon, all phenomena on Earth and in the Universe are no longer mysteries.

The Moon, very close, but we did not expect the Moon to have an extremely interesting history. Very interesting, the mystery will be opened when this part 6 is published in details.

Part 7. Laws and constants of quantum physics.

Some laws and constants of physics to confirm and popularize knowledge about quantum physics. See details in the parts that will be published.

Part 8. Scientific inventions based on Quantum code.

Some scientific inventions and new technology, especially important that you are about to receive, will make life better.

2. CONTENT.

Part 3. TRANZERAR is origin of the Universe, locate it by a device.

Analyzing observed data in the area of 93 billion light years, combine with the quantum structure of the universe, we have discovered that the Universe is formed and operated according to Quantum laws as follows:

1. Level of celestial bodies in the Universe.

Level	Name	Description	Mass (Kg)
1	Asteroid	Celestial body with any shape, not enough mass to form a sphere	$< \sim 10^{19}$
2	Small planet	Celestial body has enough mass to form a sphere, Quantum inside creates energy at low level	$3,7 \cdot 10^{19} \sim 10^{22}$
3	Medium planet	Celestial body with Quantum inside create moderate energy, create little geological activity, have conditions for life	$10^{22} \sim 10^{25}$
4	Big planet	Big celestial body with Quantum inside create big energy, create many geological activities, create belt structures	$10^{25} \sim 2,4 \cdot 10^{28}$
5	Star	Massive celestial body, Quantum inside is strong active, strong energy release, shining	$2,6 \cdot 10^{28} \sim 6,6 \cdot 10^{32}$
5*	Sun	The Sun is a medium star in the Universe	$\sim 2 \cdot 10^{30}$
6	Black Star	Massive celestial body, is Star but has a larger density than Star, so light is held by gravity	$7,5 \cdot 10^{30} \sim 10^{36}$
7	Black Ball	Supermassive celestial body, has a strong gravity to holds everything that comes near, including light, is the center of galaxies	$10^{36} \sim 10^{54}$
7*	Sagittarius A*	The center of Milky Way galaxy is a medium Black Ball in the Universe	$\sim 3 \cdot 10^{42}$
8	Tranzerar	Massive celestial body beyond imagination, is the origin of everything in the Universe	$\sim 10^{90}$

Celestial bodies level 2-8, structured by Quantum, have a Quantum core and outer layers, the structure of each layer depends on the mass (see part 1 for more details).

2. Galaxies and Milky Way.

The structure of galaxy is formed and operated by Quantum, similar to the Solar System published in part 2. It is much larger so it has some other properties as follows:

+ Sagittarius A*, the center of the Milky Way is a celestial body level 7, is the mother of the child celestial bodies from level 6 to other small one, is also the mother of the Sun.

+ Observing the universe, we see that the spiral disk galaxies are common, due to structure by Quantum, the inner orbital bodies move faster than the outer orbital bodies in sequence, (some have unusual shapes due to collisions and mergers).

+ Based on quantum structure, analyzing the movement rules of stars, we can accurately calculate the age of a galaxy.

3. Star operates according to quantum cycle.

(see details in parts 1-2).

The larger the mass of the Star, the faster the Quantum inside creates energy, so the cycle time is shorter. The cycle is divided into three periods.

No.	Describe the period	Color temperature
1	The period when the Star releases strong energy (nova explosion), on the surface generates a lot of energy, color temperature is very high 7,500-30,000K Hydrogen is blown into space and loses a lot of it, so the Star diameter is reduced	Blue-white
2	The period when the Star accumulates energy, surface color temperature decreasing, to about 4,000-6,000K The hydrogen layer is being added by low energy release frequent, the Star diameter is getting bigger and bigger	Yellow-orange
3	The period when the Star accumulates to the end stage, color temperature about 2,000-3,000K, near the time of the next strong energy release The hydrogen layer was create very thick, the Star diameter to maximum	Red

4. Celestial body level 5-6, when is it a Star? when is it a Black Star?

Observing the Universe, case of two celestial bodies of equal mass, but one is seen bright called Star, other one cannot see because it is dark, called Black Star (old name is Black Hole). This mystery is very common in the universe and is decoded by physics as follows:

Star	Black Star
<ul style="list-style-type: none">+ The hydrogen layer is very thick, beyond the light-holding diameter, energy transferred from inside to outside of hydrogen surface, then the light escapes the surface and come our eyes to see+ A Star will turn into a Black Star when it comes to time of strong energy release (nova explosion), hydrogen is blown into space and loses a lot of it, so the outer diameter is reduced, if it is smaller than the light-holding diameter, the light is held and cannot escape from the surface+ A star will turn into a Black Star when it merges with another celestial body and reaches a mass large enough to hold light	<ul style="list-style-type: none">+ The hydrogen layer is thin, within the light-holding diameter, so the light on surface is held and cannot come to our eyes+ A Black Star will turn into a Star when the quantum operation creates a lot of hydrogen, until the hydrogen layer is thick enough to emit light same a star

5. TRANZERAR is the origin of the Universe.

Tranzerar is a great celestial body of level 8, operated by Quantum, and gave birth to the majestic universe structure as follows:

Tranzerar is the mother, gave birth to the child celestial bodies from level 7 to other small one, is also the mother of Sagittarius A*, the center of Milky Way.

Currently, humans can observe an area of 93 billion light years, inside the Tranzerar disk structure, which has a diameter about 10^{35} billion light years.

Based on the Quantum law of the Universe structure, analyzing the movement of galaxies, will be determined the direction of Tranzerar, focus in that direction and search for Quantum gravity induction, will be located Tranzerar.

Tranzerar has great mass, has enough power to synthesize Quantum, is the origin of atoms and all particles in the Universe.

We need to invent the device of Quantum gravity induction to detect celestial bodies far beyond the range of electromagnetic radiation.

6. The Tranzerar Universe operated by Quantum.

Tranzerar gave birth to billion billion billion of galaxies orbiting it, including the Milky Way, and many other celestial bodies.

Sagittarius A* gave birth to billions of star systems orbiting it, including the Solar System, and many other celestial bodies.

The Sun gave birth to the planetary system orbiting it, including the Earth.

Earth is a planet level 3, so has not gave birth anything orbiting it.

Jupiter, Saturn,... are planet level 4, gave birth to the belt structure orbiting them.

Other unusual structures are due to collisions or mergers, so they have not keep the original disk structure.

X. Tranzerar operates the Universe Quantum cycle.

This section will be published in part 4, after the publication of part 1 “decoding Quantum”.

Above, have published many physical data, many new discoveries. Scientific community can verify the facts.

See details of next part in the separate publication.

Holding the Quantum code, nothing is mysterious anymore.

Send email, I will decode all the mysteries of science.

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